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Editor's Note

In the world of fine and performing arts, research is the cornerstone of understanding and preserving the rich tapestry of traditions and cultural heritage. It is through research that we gain insights into the past, decipher the intricacies of art forms, and ensure their continuity into the future. The knowledge and understanding derived from research not only enhance our appreciation but also serve as a bridge between tradition and innovation, enabling the fine and performing arts to evolve and flourish.

In this issue of "*Smṛti*," we proudly present a collection of articles that exemplify the importance of research in the field of Indian music and culture. Our contributors have dedicated their efforts to understand the nuances, and shed light on the historical and cultural contexts that shape the diverse world of fine and performing arts.

The first article of the issue is "The Oral Tradition of Rāga Rāmakali in South Indian and North Indian Music" by S. Suchitra, providing an insight on the oral tradition of the rāga in the both classical music traditions of India. Following this, Lakshmipriya R offers an in-depth analysis of the "Rāga Lakṣaṇa of Kēdāragauḷa," giving a comprehensive overview of this rāga and its nuances.

In "Nō: The Traditional Theater of Japan" by Abhinav Verma, underscoring the universal appeal of the performing arts, the author provides a cross-cultural perspective on Japanese Theater.

Sujay Shanbhag, in "An Analytical Study of Caturvidha Abhinaya in Belur Temple of Hoysala Period," throws light on the intricate temple art and abhinaya elements of our heritage.

As we continue, Pranathi G gives a comprehensive understanding of "Śrīrāga," and P Soundarya Lahari provides insights into the "Rāga-s in Sabhārañjani."

Our exploration widens with Ms. Bhairavi M's "A Study On Kīzvēḷūr Meenakshi Sundaram Pillai's Compositions," giving a glimpse into the compositions of the composer.

Dr. M Subhashree's "ஷப்தம் என்னும் இசை உருவகை"/"Ṣabdam Eṇṇum Isai Uruvakai" offers a unique perspective on the dance musical form - Ṣabdam.

Dr. Uma Kumar delves into the "Cultural Contributions of Chieftains of Yelahanka," highlighting the cultural heritage of Karnataka.

Lastly, Dr. Thirumarugal S Dineshkumar's "கூறைநாடு நடேச பிள்ளை இயற்றிய வர்ணங்கள் – ஓர் பார்வை" / "Kūraināḍu Naṭēsa Piḷḷai Iyaṛra Varṇaṅkaḷ – Ōr Pārvai" gives an in-depth analysis of the Varṇa-s composed by Kūraināḍu Naṭēsa Piḷḷai.

Dr. Rajshri Ramakrishna

Chief Editor

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Rāga Lakṣaṇa of Kēdāragauḷa – An OverviewAuthor**Dr. Rajshri Ramakrishna**Associate Professor and Head i/c
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Department of Indian Music
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The rāga Kēdāragauḷa has a long line of history and has been a part of the South Indian music tradition for many centuries. This rāga offers a wide scope for development in terms of manōdharmā saṅgīta as well as kalpita saṅgīta. There are many compositions in this rāga by various composers belonging to different time periods and such compositions have become a part of the concert repertoire of the present-day. This article attempts to trace the historical evolution of the rāga Kēdāragauḷa and aims to study the lakṣaṇa of the rāga as mentioned in the earlier period in comparison to that of the lakṣaṇa of the present-day. For the purpose of this study, the description of the rāga given in various treatises as well as the notations of different compositions in this rāga as given in the works of the 20th century have been taken up.

Keywords: Kedaragaula, Raga Laksana, Tyagaraja, Muttusvami Dikshita, Aroha, Avaroha, Treatises, Harikedaragaula.

Introduction:

In the present day, the rāga Kēdāragauḷa is a janya of the 28th mēḷakarta Harikāmbhōji.¹ It is an auḍava-sampūrṇa rāga, where the svara-s gāndhāra and niṣāda are omitted in the ārōha. In avarōha, all the seven svara-s are present. The svara-s taken by this rāga are as follows: Ṣaḍja, catuśruti ṛṣabha, antara gāndhāra, śuddha madhyama, pañcama and kaiśiki niṣāda.

The ārōha and the avarōha of the rāga Kēdāragauḷa are as follows:

S R2 M1 P N2 Ś - Ś N2 D2 P M1 G3 R2 S

¹ P Sambamoorthy, South Indian Music – Book III, Edition 6, The Indian Music Publishing House, Chennai, 1964.

Kēdāragauḷa is a gamaka-oriented rāga. In such rāga-s, the specific gamaka-s prescribed for the svara-s determine the identity or the lakṣaṇa of the rāga. In Kēdāragauḷa, ṛṣabha, madhyama and niṣāda are rendered with kampita gamaka in the ārōha. However, in certain phrases, these svara-s can be rendered as plain notes as well. For example, madhyama and niṣāda occur as jaṅṭa svara-s in certain prayōga-s and in such phrases, they predominantly occur as plain notes.

With this brief introduction of the present day lakṣaṇa of the rāga, the historical evolution of the raga is taken up.

History of Kēdāragauḷa

The rāga Kēdāragauḷa has been described in the treatise Svaramēlakalānidhi of Rāmāmātya (SMK), written in 1550 AD. In SMK, this rāga has been described as a mēḷa with all the seven svara-s. However, Rāmāmātya mentions the presence of a higher variety of niṣāda which would result in the correspondence of this mēḷa to that of the 29th mēḷakarta of the present day, which is Dhīraśaṅkarābharaṇam.

The treatise Rāgatālacintāmaṇi of Pōlūri Gōvindakavi (RTC) written during the early part of the 17th century, which follows SMK, also describes the rāga Kēdāragauḷa similar to the description given in SMK. Saṅgīta Sudha (SS) of Gōvinda Dīkṣita, written in 1614 AD, also describes Kēdāragauḷa as a mēḷa but Gōvinda Dīkṣita suggests the presence of kaiśiki niṣāda and not kākali niṣāda. All the three treatises that mention Kēdāragauḷa as a mēḷa also mention a rāga in the same name as a janya under the mēḷa, which suggests that a mēḷa is considered to be different from a rāga.

Caturdaṇḍiprakāśikā of Vēṅkaṭamakhi (CDP), written during the early part of the 17th century, is the first treatise to describe Kēdāragauḷa as a janya rāga. Vēṅkaṭamakhi states that

this rāga is a janya of the mēḷa Kāmbhōji, which would correspond to the 28th mēḷakarta of the present-day, that is Harikāmbhōji.

Rāgalakṣaṇamu of Śāhaji (RL-S), written in 1684 AD, describes Kēdāragauḷa as a janya of the mēḷa Kāmbhōji. Śāhaji, however states that the svara gāndhāra alone is omitted in the ārōha, making it a śāḍava-sampūrṇa rāga. While giving the illustrative phrases for this rāga, Śāhaji has mentioned the following phrase as an āyitta prayōga: RMPNNDNSNDPMPNNS, where dhaivata occurs as a vakra svara in the ārōha phrase RMPNNDNS. This is immediately followed by the descending phrase NDPMPNNS, where dhaivata is omitted in the ārōha.

The 18th century treatises like Rāgalakṣaṇa of Muddu Vēṅkaṭamakhi (RL-MV) and Saṅgrahacūḍāmaṇi (SCūḍ) describe the rāga Kēdāragauḷa as close as possible to its form of the present-day. According to these treatises, Kēdāragauḷa is an auḍava-sampūrṇa rāga. However, while RL-MV describes this rāga as the 28th mēḷa or rāgāṅga rāga, taking the prefix ‘Hari’ for the purpose of Kaṭapayādi, making it Harikēdāragauḷa, SCūḍ mentions this rāga as a janya of the 28th mēḷakarta Harikāmbhōji. RL-MV describes Kēdāragauḷa as a rakti rāga. The treatises Mahābharatcūḍāmaṇi and Saṅgītasārasaṅgrahamu of Tiruvēṅkaṭakavi follow the tradition of SCūḍ and describe Kēdāragauḷa as a janya of the 28th mēḷakarta Harikāmbhōji.

The lakṣaṇa of this rāga is also available in the works Saṅgītasampradāyapradarśiṇi of Subbarāma Dīkṣita (SSP – 1904 AD) and Kṛtīmaṇimālai of Rangaramanuja Ayyangar which give the notations for compositions. In Saṅgītasampradāyapradarśiṇi, Subbarāma Dīkṣita follows the description given in RL-MV and mentions Kēdāragauḷa as the 28th rāgāṅga rāga. Subbarāma Dīkṣita states that the svara-s ṛṣabha, madhyama, niṣāda and gāndhāra are the jīva svara-s that provide rañjana. This rāga has been classified as a rakti rāga in SSP. ²

² Subbarāma Dīkṣitar - Saṅgītasampradāyapradarśiṇi, Vol 2, Vidyā Vilāsini Press, Eṭṭaiyapuram Samasthānam, Eṭṭaiyapuram, 1905.

The twentieth century work Kṛtimaṇimālai of Rangaramanuja Ayyangar gives the description for the rāga Kēdāragauḷa. Rangaramanuja Ayyangar describes this rāga as a janya of the mēḷakarta Harikāmbhōji. The ārōha-avarōha of the rāga is:

S R M P N Ś Ś N D P M G R S.

There is a note by the author stating that the phrase ‘RGGM RGRS’ is a special prayōga which provides rañjana to this rāga.³ This phrase however, is not seen in compositions as well as manōdharma saṅgīta in the present day.

In ancient Tamiz history, the paṇ Gāndhāra Pañcamam is said to be an equivalent of the rāga Kēdāragauḷa. This paṇ has been widely used in many Tēvāram-s. Coṟṟuṇai Vēdiyan, a widely known Namaccivāya Padigam of Tirunāvukkarasar is set in this paṇ. The paṇ Gāndhāra Pañcamam has also been handled by the other composers of Tēvāram, namely Tiruñāna Sambandhar and Sundarar. With this brief history, different compositions in the rāga Kēdāragauḷa have been taken up for study.

Compositions in Kēdāragauḷa

Kēdāragauḷa is one of the few rāga-s to have been handled by the musical trinity, namely Tyāgarāja, Muttusvāmi Dīkṣita and Śyāma Śāstri. Tuḷasi bilva, a kṛti of Tyāgarāja in this rāga, set to ādi tāḷa is a well-known composition and another kṛti of his, Vēṇugāna lōluni, set to rūpaka tāḷa is also a composition which has been part of the concert repertoire. The contrast in the tāḷa-s of the two kṛti-s suggest the range of the rāga Kēdāragauḷa which can be established in a short tāḷa like rūpaka as well as expounded in a longer tāḷa like ādi. Apart from the two kṛti-s mentioned above, Tyāgarāja has composed various kṛti-s in this rāga, which are listed below⁴:

³ Raṅgarāmānuja Ayyaṅgār, Śrī Kṛtimaṇimālai Part 1, Sabarmathi, Egmore, Chennai, 1947.

⁴ T S Parthasarathy, Sri Tyagaraja Svami Kirttanaigal - Edition 8, The Karnatic Music Book Centre, Chennai, July

1. Karuṇājaladhi – Cāpu
2. Ō jagannātha - Ādi
3. Vanaja nayanuḍani – Ādi
4. Siggumāli - Ādi
5. Vārija nayana – Ādi (Prahāda bhakti vijaya)
6. Vārija nayana – Ādi (Divya nāma)
7. Rāmuni maravakavē – Ādi (Divya nāma)
8. Dharmātma nannipuḍu – Jhampa (Divya nāma)
9. Raghunandana – Rūpaka (Divya nāma)
10. Lāli lālayya – Jhampa (Utsava sampradaya)
11. Mā rāmacandruniki – Ādi (Maṅgaḷa kṛti - Utsava Sampradāya)

In SSP, two compositions of Muttusvāmi Dīkṣita are available namely, Abhayāmbikāyāh set to miśra jhampa tāḷa and Nīlakaṅṭham bhajēham set to rūpaka tāḷa. In Nīlakaṅṭham bhajēham, Dīkṣita brings out the rāga mudra in the caraṇa – Nāmarūpa vicitrataṛa dakṣataram īsvaram Kēdāragauḷa priyakaram, where he states that Lord Śiva is delighted by the rāga Kēdāragauḷa.

Parākēla nannu, set to ādi tāḷa is a composition which is believed to have been composed by Śyāmā Śāstri. However, the analyses of the melodic, lyrical as well as the structural setting of this composition have led to different views with respect to the authorship of this composition, with musicologists suggesting that this kṛti is of a composer from Śyāma Śāstri's lineage and not his own.

Kēdāragauḷa has been handled by post-trinity composers like Rāmanāthapuram Śrīnivāsa Ayyaṅgār, Pāpanāsam Śivan and so on. The kṛti-s Saragunapālimpa and Sāmikku sari evvarē are well-known kṛti-s and have been in vogue in the concert repertoire.

Apart from kṛti-s, there are different musical forms available in Kēdāragauḷa like gīta-s, varṇa-s and pada-s. Bhāmarō muvvaḡōpāla is a pada of Kṣētrayya in this rāga. Tiruvotṭriyūr Tyāḡayyar's ādi tāḷa varṇa, Sāmi Dayajūdarā, is another well-known composition. Incidentally, the Pallavi, Anupallavi as well as the Muktāyi svāra of this varṇa have tāra sthāyi ṣaḍja as the graha svāra. It is interesting to note that the graha svāra of the third ettugaḍa svāra is dhaivata. This is a rare feature which is not often seen in compositions. The melody however, only descends from dhaivata.

Gōvindasāmayya, who is believed to have been a pre-trinity composer, has composed a varṇa in this rāga, Nīsari mandedora which is set to ādi tāḷa. The notation of this composition is available in the appendix of SSP. There are some interesting features in this varṇa. The eḍuppu of this varṇa occurs at the beat of the little finger instead of sama and the caraṇa begins at the beat of the third finger. All the ciṭṭavāra-s have sāhitya and the last ciṭṭasvāra alone has both sollukaṭṭu or jati as well as sāhitya. The caraṇa begins with gāndhāra, which is yet another rare feature not seen in other compositions. Here too, the melody only descends from gāndhāra. Another varṇa, namely Viribhōṇi of Rudrapaṭṇam Vēṅkaṭarāmayya set to jhampa tāḷa is also set in Kēdāragauḷa.

The compositions of Kṣētrayya as well as other pre-trinity composers suggest that the rāga Kēdāragauḷa is an older rāga which has been in vogue for many centuries.

This rāga is said to be a uttarāṅga pradhāna rāga, where emphasis is given to the phrases ranging in the upper madhya sthāyi and tāra sthāyi. This is evident from the compositions like Abhayāmbikāyāh, Parākēla nannu, Sāmikku Sari evvare as well as the varṇa of Tiruvotṭriyūr

Tyāgayya, all of which begin with tāra sthāyi ṣaḍja. Even in the compositions like Tuḷasi bilva and Vēṇugāna lōluni where the pallavi starts in madhya sthāyi ṛṣabha, the melody of the anupallavi is predominantly set in the tāra sthāyi.

In concerts today, Kēdāragauḷa is often taken up for extemporising. This rāga offers ample scope for development in terms of manōdharma saṅgīta. This rāga also offers scope for viruttam-s in concerts.

Conclusion

- Kēdāragauḷa is an older rāga which has been a part of the South Indian music tradition for a long time.
- In the earlier period, Kēdāragauḷa was considered to be a mēḷa with all the seven svāra-s in both ārōha and avarōha. The later treatises, however classify this rāga as a janya of the 28th mēḷakarta of the present day, Harikāmbhōji.
- This auḍava-sampūrṇa rāga has ṛṣabha, madhyama and niṣāda as jīva and nyāsa svāra-s, which are predominantly rendered with kampita gamaka. The svāra-s madhyama and niṣāda also occur as jaṅṭa svāra-s in certain phrases and in such a case, they occur as plain notes.
- There are various musical forms available in this rāga ranging from the pre-trinity to the post-trinity period. These compositions have become an integral part of the concert repertoire of the present day.
- This rāga offers ample scope for extemporisation in terms of the different aspects of manōdharma singing like niraval, ālāpana, tāna, kalpana svāra-s, viruttam-s and so on.

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